

GEORGIA'S ENERGY SECURITY ASSESSMENT AND KEY CHALLENGES**Arabidze N.***Associate Professor**Georgian Technical University, Faculty of Power Engineering, Head of Thermal Energy, Energy Efficient Technologies and Energy Audit Department
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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15115124>***Abstract**

Georgia has a strategic location in the South Caucasus region and serves as an energy corridor. Energy transit through Georgia is carried out both from east to west (from Azerbaijan to Turkey and the Black Sea ports in other countries), and from north to south from Russia to Armenia and Turkey. The oil pipelines (Baku-Tbilisi-Supsa and Baku-Tbilisi-Ceyhan) and the gas pipeline (Baku-Tbilisi-Erzurum) as well as the South Caucasus pipeline from Russia to Armenia are distinguished by their transit function. Georgia also performs an electricity transit function. It is worth noting that the combination of the functions of the energy corridor should ensure that there is no shortage of access to energy resources in the country, however, as history shows, the strategic location of the country is not a guarantee of the country's energy security and additional measures are needed to ensure the country's energy resources.

Keywords: Georgia, Energy Security, Renewable Energy, Energy Policy.

1. Introduction:

After the collapse of the Soviet Union, in the 1990s, Georgia's energy system faced significant challenges. The country had to meet its energy demand on its own while maintaining its energy infrastructure in working order. Social deprivation, high crime rates, low wages, and in many cases, even non-existence, further complicated the energy problems. As a result, electricity was characterized by frequent outages and long-term emergency situations. In addition, access to fuel resources was limited, and the collapse of the centralized heating system sharply increased the demand for fuel resources. Given that household energy demand could not be met by either electricity or fuel resources, the population often resorted to alternative sources of energy, such as firewood, kerosene stoves, and cheap gas heaters. The use of cheap and low-quality equipment, often imported from neighboring countries, increased the risk of accidents, and due to the lack of regulations, it was practically impossible to combat it. Due to malfunctions in metering and supply systems, electricity was often stolen and arbitrarily connected to the network. Fuel resources were supplied to the population for a certain period of time by trucks with gas and kerosene tanks. Due to the lack of safety equipment, the population, who went to get fuel in their own containers, often became victims of accidents. It should also be noted that fuel resources were often supplied in this way at an unfair price, since only a few companies had a monopoly on the supply of fuel resources.

Active gasification, which began in the 2000s, eliminated the need for fuel resources to be supplied by the previous method, although this is still a problem in some high-mountainous regions. One alternative to supplying fuel resources was the use of firewood. A

significant part of the population used wood-burning stoves even in large cities. The increase in demand for firewood contributed to the rapid deforestation, and under the then dysfunctional legal system, the process was difficult to control, and in some cases, practically impossible. Another argument for the need for energy independence and a diversified energy market is the sabotage of the 1,200 mm diameter gas pipeline and the 700 mm backup pipeline connecting Russia and Georgia on January 22, 2006. The same event coincided with the failure of the 500 kV "Kavkasioni" power transmission line. The interruption of access to energy on such a scale paralyzed part of Georgia. Part of the population of Tbilisi also lost electricity. The then Ministry of Energy immediately began importing electricity from Turkey. The sabotage of the gas pipeline was particularly painful for the part of the population that used natural gas for heating and cooking. In the 2000s, talk also began about the Khudoni HPP, the idea of which was formed back in the 80s of the last century. The installed capacity of the hydroelectric power plant would be 704 megawatts, which is a particularly large capacity for the Georgian energy system and, accordingly, this project is also strategically important. However, due to the scale of the hydroelectric power plant, a part of the population, due to the possible impact, developed a negative mood, which turned into a protest. According to the new agreement signed in 2007, the construction of the hydroelectric power plant was supposed to begin in 2011, although the issue of the hydroelectric power plant is still under discussion. The Namakhvan HPP project, which has also been temporarily suspended, faced a similar challenge.

Therefore, Georgia has established the main priority areas that need to be addressed to strengthen energy security:

1. Reducing dependence on energy imports;
2. Diversifying import sources;
3. Strengthening the country's domestic and imported energy infrastructure and ensuring the existence of a backup infrastructure;
4. Maximizing the use of local energy resources and increasing their share in final energy consumption;

3. Analysis of the current energy situation

According to the 2023 energy balance (National Statistical Office of Georgia, 2020), domestic energy supply amounted to 237,601.2 terajoules, and final energy consumption was 215,034.8 terajoules. The household sector is in first place in terms of energy consumption, which consumed 66,406.4 terajoules of energy in the same year. Up to 70% of the energy consumed by households comes from natural gas, while electricity accounts for only 15%. In addition, energy exports amounted to 21,108.5 terajoules in 2023 (of which almost 100% is electricity). According to Georgia's energy balance, we can say that approximately 81.4% of energy comes from imports, while local generation accounts for 18.5%, of which 100% comes from electricity, and more than 70% from hydropower.

The installed capacity of the Georgian electric system is 4,467 MW, of which 1,189 MW comes from thermal power plants, 21 MW from wind power plants, 2,381 MW from regulating hydroelectric power plants, 592 MW from seasonal hydroelectric power plants and 284 MW from small-capacity power plants.

Although Georgia's energy policy is focused on the use of renewable energy sources and the total capacity of hydroelectric power plants exceeds that of thermal power plants, the share of thermal energy in final energy consumption is still high (in 2024, the total output of thermal power plants amounted to 2082.58 billion kWh, which is 14.63% of the total output). It is worth noting that such a percentage may be small in the annual cycle, however, since hydro resources account for a larger share of the installed capacity, during the winter water shortage period, their generation drops sharply and, along with the operation of thermal power plants, the need to import electricity arises. Given that almost 100% of fuel resources (natural gas and coal) are imported, the picture of energy dependence (and therefore energy security) is further exacerbated. Local electricity generation by 2024 amounted to 14.234 billion kWh. Today, Georgia does not consume natural gas imported from Russia, and in exchange for transit, the country receives monetary compensation. It can be said that this negatively affects the competitiveness of the market and the diversification of natural gas import sources, while, at the same time, dependence on Russian gas, due to a number of factors, poses a threat to energy.

As mentioned above, Georgia also performs an electricity transit function, in 2024, 1,1014.6 billion kWh of electricity was transited from Azerbaijan to Turkey through Georgia, and 59.6 billion kWh of electricity was transited from Russia to Turkey. This year, there was no electricity transit from Armenia to Turkey via Georgia.

4. Georgia's Energy Security Assessment

This policy document will use three main indicators as criteria for assessing Georgia's state energy security, which, based on statistical information, provide a picture of the state of the country's energy sector. These criteria are:

1. Import Dependence Ratio (IDR): According to the latest available energy balance, Georgia is 80% dependent on imports. This indicator differs from the pure import dependence (85.4%) given above, since the import dependence index is reduced by the share of exported energy. Georgia exports energy mainly during the dry season (April-July).

2. Energy Security Index (ESI): According to the Energy Security Index, which is calculated in a complex manner and includes both energy and economic and other social components, Georgia's index is 0.891 (the average for Europe is 1. The energy security index also has an annual downward trend of -1.12%. Compared to 1995, the energy security index has decreased by 34%, which is explained by the increase in energy imports, the decrease in domestic generation and, especially, the decrease in the share of the extractive industry, which used to be one of the most important.

3. The total duration of electricity outages during the year (SAIDI – System average interruption duration index), the frequency of electricity supply interruptions during the year (SAIFI – system average interruption frequency index) and the Herfindahl-Hirschman Index (HHI). Technical measures carried out by the Georgian State Electrosystem Modernization, which is aimed at minimizing these two indicators. The worst indicator in this component is “Energopro-Georgia”, which is an electricity distribution network in the regions. The National Energy and Water Regulatory Commission of Georgia annually monitors SAIFI and SAIDI indicators, which makes it easier for companies to identify weak points and improve their indicators annually. JSC “Telasi” recorded 6,316 outages in 2019, the total duration of which is 9 hours and 52 minutes, and the SAIFI indicator was 5.9; In the case of Joint Stock Company “Energopro-Georgia”, based on 2019 data, the planned and unplanned SAIDI indicator for internal reasons is 55 hours and 26 minutes, and a total of 42,920 outages were recorded, while the SAIFI indicator was 27.3. The need for diversification of the energy market is also reflected in the calculation of the Herfindahl-Hirschman Index (HHI), which indicates the concentration of the electricity market. Based on the above, two electricity distribution companies mainly operate in the territory of Georgia – “Telasi” and “Energy Pro-Georgia”. In addition, “Telasi” has a market share of 37%, while “Pro-Georgia” has a market share of 63%. By calculating the above with the Herfindahl-Hirschman index, we obtain: $HHI_{2019} = (37)^2 + (63)^2 = 5338$ for index values, where $HHI < HHI_{2500}$ – the market is highly concentrated. With our indicator $HHI=5338$ – it becomes clear that the electricity market is highly concentrated, which negatively affects energy security.

Given the small size of the territory of Georgia, one of the most important components of energy security is the location of objects of strategic importance that require special protection. According to the Law of

Georgia "On Engineering and Geodetic Control and Security of Objects of Special Importance and Strategic Purpose", Article 4(2) defines objects of strategic importance. Among them, energy includes: main pipelines, gas pipelines and water pipelines, high-voltage power lines (35 kW and above) and substations (110 kW and above), hydro, thermal nuclear power plants. In terms of energy infrastructure, Georgia has a low energy security index, due to the temporary occupation of Georgian territories, which is the main challenge. High-voltage (500 400 330 220 110 kilovolts) power lines are located throughout the country, mainly in the form of overhead lines, which is also a significant challenge for the country's energy sector. Of these, "Kartli-2" stands out, which is located in the territory of Shida Kartli, parallel to the Tbilisi-Gori connecting road (state highway No. 1), adjacent to the Tskhinvali region and will pass through the territories where the so-called "border zone" is located. Since the power line in question is a strategic facility, its location in this area requires additional security measures.

5. Conclusion

1. Based on the analysis of Georgia's energy balances, indicators have been identified that indicate the energy risks in the country, including: the share of imports in final energy consumption; seasonality of generation; utilization of local energy sources and, accordingly, their share in final consumption; reduction of import dependence and diversification of import sources.

2. The indicators for calculating energy security are divided into the following groups: share of resource consumption; share of exhaustible resources; share of efficient resources; share of utilization of new energy sources; share of pollution in the extraction of fossil fuels.

3. Based on statistical data, the energy security and import dependence index has been estimated.

4. The share of energy consumed by the three largest sectors of energy consumption in final consumption has been analyzed.

5. According to the market concentration - Herfindahl-Hirschman index, it has been determined that Georgia's import sources are highly concentrated.

6. The average values of Georgia's energy security indicators and index have been assessed.